

ARMY OF UZBEKISTAN

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Annotation: By 2022, the Uzbek army will take 54th place in the ranking of the armies of the world, which includes the armed forces of 106 countries of the world. [3] This is stated in the updated Global Firepower Rating.

Keywords: According to Global Fire Power (GFP) (as of March 2022), there are currently 420 in Uzbekistan tanks , 1210 armored personnel carriers , 109 missile systems, 70 fighters, 65 helicopters , in particular 25 attack helicopters and many other weapons , the number of people who can bear arms and serve in the army is over 15.7 million.

By 2022, the Uzbek army will take 54th place in the ranking of the armies of the world, which includes the armed forces of 106 countries [3]. According to the updated Global ranking Firepower , GFP based its information about Uzbekistan on the CIA website , MRB World Book of Facts , Wikipedia and other open sources. Among the countries of Central Asia, except Uzbekistan Kazakhstan is also in the ranking , where GFP ranks 80th . Afghanistan ranks 76th among the countries closest to Uzbekistan. Tajikistan , Kyrgyzstan and Turkmenistan were not included in the ranking.

Uzbekistan among the CIS countries , the Baltics and Georgia Russia (2nd place) and Ranked 3rd after Ukraine (21st place). Azerbaijan (50s) , Belarus (52), Georgia (64), Kazakhstan (80), Estonia (96) and Lithuania (103) . Countries such as Armenia, Moldova and Latvia were not included in the ranking. According to rating If the US military is considered the most powerful , The Russian and Chinese armies are in the top three . The top ten included the armies of India, Britain, France, Germany, Turkey, South Korea and Japan. It should be noted that in the GFP ranking in 2014 Uzbekistan ranked 48th. [6]

Declaration of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 31 , 1991 " On State Independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan " . The Ministry of Defense and the National Guard will be formed . The Ministry of Internal Affairs of the former USSR, the State Security Committee of the USSR and the internal troops located on the territory of the republic will be transferred to the jurisdiction of the Republic of Uzbekistan . This was enshrined in the Law of the

Republic of Uzbekistan " On the Foundations of State Independence " dated August 31 , 1991, which states that "The Republic of Uzbekistan has the right to create the Ministry of Defense, the National Guard and alternative service . In practice , thi gave the young republic the right to pursue a military policy President of the Republic of Uzbekistan The Decree of September 6, 1991 created the Ministry of Defense , which determined its staffing system and powers. By order of September 10, 1991, the Minister of Defense was appointed

commander of the National Guard. Republic of Uzbekistan_ The Decree of the Cabinet of Ministers of October 25, 1991 approved the legal status, structure and regulations of the Ministry of Defense . On the basis of the administration of the Turkestan military district, the General Staff and departments of the Ministry of Defense were created. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the fundamentals of state independence of the Republic of Uzbekistan " dated December 30 , 1991 Taking into account the suspension of funding for the troops of the former USSR from

February 1, 1992 on the basis of the Minsk Decree of the Commonwealth of Independent States on the Armed Forces and Border Troops, the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan on January 14 —On the recruitment of military units and educational institutions of the USSR Ministry of Internal Affairs located on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan » , January 14 , institutions . It provides that units, associations , branches, universities and military units of the Ministry of Internal Affairs and Defense of the former Soviet Union, located on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan , will legally be under the control of the country. The resolution provided social and legal protection for military personnel , members of their families, military personnel and pensioners who served in the former Soviet

Union. Military units and educational institutions, institutions and organizations were provided with logistical and financial support from the state .

- On March 24, 1992, by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On the units of the Border Troops located on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan ", the Department of Border Troops was created under the National Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan and parts of the Central Asian Border Troops were transferred to its disposal .

- On May 18, 1992, by the Decree " On the Airborne Troops, Military Transport Aviation, Intelligence Troops, Supply Troops located on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan ", these troops were transferred to the republican administration . Decrees of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 12, 1992 " On air defense units located on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan " , dated November 13 , 1992 "On chemical protection military units located on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan". " moved to the republic and improved in terms of quality. Thus ended the organizational period of building the Armed Forces of an independent country.

Republic of Uzbekistan in the formation of its Armed Forces in accordance with the legal norms of the United Nations (UN) , security and cooperation in Europe The Helsinki Final Act met all the requirements of international documents such as the CIS Collective Security Treaty . By the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated July 3, 1992, the Ministry of Defense was transformed into the Ministry of Defense. Laws of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Defense " adopted , " On universal military duty and military service " and " On alternative service " .

- On November 22, 1993 , the Decree of the President "On the Battle Flag of the military unit of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan" was signed , establishing a

single model of the Battle Flag of the Armed Forces . In accordance with the Law of the Supreme Council of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 29, 1993 " On the celebration of the Day of Defenders of the Fatherland " , January 14 was declared the Day of Defenders of the Fatherland .

•□The military doctrine of Uzbekistan, adopted in August 1995, determined the military policy of the country . In connection with the military-political situation in the region, on February 3, 2000, the Defense Doctrine of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted. The Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan include military units of the Ground Forces , Air Defense Forces and Air Force , Special Forces, Border and Internal Troops , the Ministry of National Security, the Ministry of Emergency Situations and other ministries and departments . Tasks of the MHX, Border Troops and the Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan . Archived 26 July 2014 at the Wayback website machine .

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